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PROFILE OF PEDESTRIAN CRASHES IN NABLUS CITY, PALESTINE

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Abstract

Pedestrians are a vulnerable group in terms of road safety. Studies in Nablus City showed a high percentage of pedestrian crashes. The objective of this research is to draw a detailed profile of pedestrian crashes in Nablus City, Palestine. Road crash data involving pedestrians for five years (2012-2016) were collected from Nablus Traffic Police Department. Data were analyzed spatially, temporally, and based on various patterns. Results showed that the highest frequency of pedestrian crashes occurred in year 2015, during the spring season, on Thursday, and in the early afternoon hours. The crashes concentrated in the city center and its perimeter zones. They also concentrated on major streets of the city. Pedestrians with an age group younger than 10 years old were the most vulnerable. A high percentage of pedestrian crashes involved public transportation vehicles. The majority of victims and drivers were males. The results were linked to socio-economic characteristics and behavior of people in the city. The vast majority of pedestrian crashes were slight injuries. Killed or seriously injured (KSI) pedestrian crashes constituted 7% with a concentration on Saturday and in the afternoon hours. The highest age groups involved in KSI crashes were younger than 10 years old and older than 40 years old. The study recommends the traffic police to computerize the data collection and archiving system, and to reallocate the limited human resources to areas with high pedestrian crashes and severity. The relevant authorities should exert awareness efforts among school children and drivers regarding road safety behavior.

Keywords: Pedestrian Crashes; Road Safety, Nablus; Palestine.

1. Introduction

People are using the transportation system as pedestrians; therefore, have the potential of being harmed if the system is not sufficiently safe. As such, walking is an important mode of transportation, which should be studied carefully to reduce the probability of facing risks.

A pedestrian, as defined for this fact, is any person on foot, walking, running, jogging, hiking, sitting, or lying down who is involved in a motor vehicle traffic crash. A traffic crash is defined as an incident that involved one or more motor vehicles where at least one vehicle was in transport and the crash originated on a public traffic way, such as a road or highway. Crashes that occurred on a private property, including parking lots and driveways, are not considered here (NHTSA, 2014). “Pedestrians are parts of every roadway environment, and attention should be paid to their presence in rural as well as urban areas, ... pedestrians are the lifeblood of our urban areas, especially in the downtown and other retail areas” (AASHTO, 2001).

Pedestrian safety is one of the most critical concerns in transportation safety. In order to overcome or reduce crashes, studies should be prepared at the critical locations where pedestrian crashes are relatively high or severe. As stated by Litman (2007), an improved pedestrian safety and safer walkable environment help the community to improve accessibility for non-drivers, reduce the cost of transportation, enhance parking efficiency, improve aesthetics, save the land needed for road construction, reduce the level of pollution, and support public transportation.

Previous local researches about pedestrians’ safety are somehow few in the West Bank of Palestine with no adequate studies about pedestrians’ safety issues. During the last years, there was nearly a steady number of traffic crashes, and the same for the percentage of pedestrian crashes in the West Bank. The Higher Traffic

Council's reports showed that pedestrian crashes were 5383 between 2011 and 2014, forming 17.5% of total crashes (Higher Traffic Council, 2012-2015). On the other hand, pedestrians' safety studies or official interventions are very limited in Palestine, and they were only used as static indicators from the Police Departments so that the Higher Traffic Council could use them in its annual reports. The pedestrian crash data are recorded manually in the police reports with low accuracy in the recording crash details. The frequency of road crashes and deaths had increased in the past few years in Nablus City. Furthermore, there was no detailed pedestrian safety study yet in Palestine.

As a general observation, police enforcement is generally weak and is concentrated in the critical locations of city centers, major intersections, and near school areas; the available human resources is limited. In Palestinian cities, it is generally common that pedestrians do not strictly abide by the traffic rules within the roadway network. Pedestrians usually cross streets randomly and from undesignated areas. They might sometimes even cross the street at signalized intersections before waiting for the pedestrian signal. In addition, the pedestrian facilities (signs, markings, sidewalks, etc.) are generally in weak conditions and need maintenance. Pedestrian crossings are not well placed in the proper locations and sometimes non-existing. Furthermore, awareness of traffic rules is not common among young children.

As such, the main objectives of this study are to prepare detailed profile of pedestrian crashes in the most hazardous zones in Nablus City, and to provide general recommendations to improve the level of pedestrian safety in terms of data collection, safety programs, and appropriate countermeasures.

2. Study Area

The study area is Nablus City, which is one of the most settled cities in the West Bank. It has a population of more than 150,000 inhabitants (Palestinian Central Bureau of Statistics, 2017). It is located between two steep mountains; Eibal on the north and Jerzeem on the south. Thus, the extension of the city is towards the east and the west directions, which makes the network of highways, especially the major corridors, concentrated in a longitudinal direction connecting east with west. Figure 1 shows the study area.

Nablus City is considered a vital commercial and service center in the West Bank. It has a high concentration of commercial centers and traditional industries, the largest university in the West Bank, and it hosts other historical, educational, cultural, financial, and medical institutions. The city is visited by large numbers of people for medication, business, work, trading, and higher education purposes. Therefore, consideration should be taken regarding its pedestrian traffic system and their safety issues. Nablus City road network forms the shape of longitudinal network from east to west, as indicated before. For instance, Al Quds St. and its extensions (Faisal St. and Haifa St.) are considered arterial roads and gates for Nablus City for the eastern and southern localities and governorates. Moreover, Rafedia St. is another arterial street linking the CBD area with Rafedia area, to reach the New Campus of An-Najah National University, which also extends to the western localities and governorates. In addition to these, there are several collector roads such as Amman St., Al Makhfia St., Tunis St., Jaffa St., etc., which are considered as vital roads in the city.

3. Summary of Selected Previous Studies

The following studies provide some insight towards achieving the objectives of this research. The studies showed that there is clear interest in pedestrian safety issues all over the world, searching for causes and trying to minimize, as much as possible, the pedestrian crashes and fatalities. The word "crash" is used in this study instead of "accident" according to Garber and Hoel (2009), Davis (2001), and WHO (2004) explanations.

In 2013, there were 4,735 pedestrians killed and an estimated 66,000 injuries in traffic crashes in the United States; constituting 4,653 traffic crashes each had one or more pedestrian fatalities. On the average, a pedestrian was killed every 2 hours and injured every 8 minutes in traffic crashes (Fatality Analysis Reporting System, 2013). Going through the year of 2015 the NHTSA statistics showed that there were 5,376 pedestrians killed and an estimated 70,000 injured in traffic crashes. A total of 5,295 traffic crashes had one or more pedestrian fatalities. On average, a pedestrian was killed every 1.6 hours and injured every 7.5 minutes in traffic crashes. NHTSA studied these crashes and constructed a profile contained the environmental characteristics, time of day and day of week, age, gender, type of vehicles, and fatalities by cities and states (NHTSA, 2015). The number increased in 2016 to reach 5987 pedestrian killed.

Figure 1: Ortho-photo for Nablus City (source: Geomolg, 2017)

Zegeer (2001), Knoblauch (2001), Tracy (2012), and Igazvölgyi (2015) helped in defining the locations of the study, wherever they were in mid-blocks or intersections, and concentrating on how a crash could be explained by the behavior of pedestrian in interacting with the road. Andreou (2009) highlighted on the importance of location and age of victims, which will be investigated in in this study.

Obeng-Atuah (2016) showed that pedestrian fatalities constituted 42% of road traffic fatalities in Ghana, and 68% of the total pedestrian fatalities were related to pedestrian crossing facilities and behavior. The study examined the state of pedestrian crossing facilities (crosswalks) and behavior on urban roads in Ghana, and its consequences on pedestrian safety. A 5-year road traffic collision data, information on the condition and utilization of cross walks, and pedestrians' perceptions of cross-walks located at different land uses were collected and analyzed. Findings showed that 98% of pedestrian collisions occurred in locations further away from crosswalks.

The NHTSA (2015) and Vision Zero (2013) reported some quantitative data such as number of crashes, rates, and other environmental characteristics, which could be beneficial to make comparisons with the area of this study. In addition, they provided a sound methodology of showing the results in what is called "Profiles" presenting who, where, when, and other questions related to pedestrian crashes.

The study of Al-Masaeid (2009) was conducted in a somewhat similar environment to Palestine; therefore, a comparison with it would be helpful. The GIS tool of Al-Omari (2013) would be a reliable way to present and analyze the results. Locally, there were limited studied related to the objectives of this study, but those studies formed a good background. These will allow for comparing the results of this thesis with those studies such as the studies of Kobari (2000) and Khader (2014) since both are in the same area of study with somewhat similar scope.

4. Methodology

Studies that have dealt with the safety of pedestrians are limited in Palestine. The lack of proper pedestrian environment and services would lead to ignoring this important matter. Therefore, studies should be done such as this one to analyze the pedestrian safety as a step to develop a pedestrian safety action plan. The objective of this study is related to the safety of the pedestrians in Nablus City, which is one of the main concerns of the transportation engineers and decision makers. The components of the methodology to achieve the objectives are the following.

Literature Review: Desk studies and internet research to review existing publications, studies, and literature related to pedestrian safety for different locations around the world.

Data Collection: In this study, data of pedestrian crashes for a 5-year period from 2012 to 2016 in collaboration with the Department of Traffic Accidents in the Police Directorate of Nablus were collected. This database was used in analyzing the pedestrian safety study conditions in the study area. The crash data are filled manually in the Police Directorate of Nablus, the information is hand-written by the police officers, which was a challenge. Therefore, careful attention had to be paid to obtain accurate information, as much as possible.

This information includes: Time and date of crash (date, day, and hour), location, demographic parameters for parties involved, severity, and type of vehicles involved. There were some other information to be collected from different sources, such as GIS shape files, maps, demographic statistics about geographic areas in Nablus City, zoning for the study area, and population for the period of analysis (2012-2016).

Data Analysis: After the collection of data for the five-year study period, necessary analysis was done to evaluate and to study the profile of pedestrian safety at the different locations. Pedestrian crash profiles for Nablus City were developed including zones spatially, temporally, and the demographic distributions of crashes.

Finally, several recommendations were set based on the data analysis and reviewing safety conditions, in coordinating with stakeholders, resources, and potentials.

5. Pedestrian Crash Profile

The year 2015 had the highest pedestrian crashes. It was higher by about 15% than the yearly average crashes; however, the total pedestrian crashes decreased in the following year (2016). The yearly distribution of pedestrian crashes during the period of analysis is shown in Figure 2. After reviewing what happened in the city, which could affect the pedestrian crashes increase, there were no significant issues regarding pedestrian movement, so this increase was with no apparent reason.

Figure 2. Total Pedestrian Crashes in Nablus City by Year

In terms of the monthly distribution of pedestrian crashes during the study period, Figure 3 illustrates this. May was the critical month with 106 crashes with a percent of 10.3%, and then came March, August, and April with 99, 99, and 98 crashes, respectively. Approximately 29.4% of the crashes occurred in the spring season (March, April, and May). On the other hand, winter had the lowest percentage with 19.3% only. These results are logical

due to the obvious and active pedestrian movements all over the city in spring or summer seasons, unlike winter or autumn.

Figure 3. Distribution of Pedestrian Crashes in Nablus City by Month

Furthermore, Thursday was the day of the week with the highest pedestrian crashes in the city with 18.4%, as it is the end of weekdays with active shopping and entertainment activities. On the other hand, Friday was the lowest with 10.5% only from the total pedestrian crashes in the city, as shown in Figure 4. Friday is the weekly holiday with limited street activities.

Figure 4. Distribution of Pedestrian Crashes in Nablus City by Day

As for the hour of occurrence, it is clear that the crashes fluctuated from one hour to another, with a concentration around mid-day and in the afternoon to the evening hours (12:00 to 19:00), which formed 56.5% of the total pedestrian crashes. The most critical hour was from 13:00 to 14:00, which contained 111 crashes with a percent of 11.1% from the total, as shown in Figure 4.

In terms of age of victims, for those younger than 17 years old, their percentage was 58.8% and they were involved in 52.8% of pedestrian crashes. It was clear that children with the age of 10 years old or younger were the most vulnerable group, as those were involved in highest number of crashes among all. On the other hand, those older than 60 formed 8.6% from the total population and were involved in 8.8% of the total pedestrian crashes (see Figure 6). This leads to the fact that the number of pedestrian crashes and pedestrians' age is inversely proportional.

Figure 5. Distribution of Pedestrian Crashes in Nablus City by Hour

Figure 6. Distribution of Pedestrian Crashes in Nablus City by Victim's Age

It is also interesting to notice that the peak hour of the pedestrian crashes occurred at 1:00 PM and the highest age group involved in the crashes were children 10 years old and younger. Furthermore, and as will be presented later, some school areas had high number of pedestrian crashes. This leads to the conclusion that children of primary schools are one of the vulnerable groups.

By analyzing the gender of victims or drivers, it was found that 67% of the victims were males and 33% were females. On the other hand, the drivers who were involved in the crashes in Nablus City were mostly males with a percent of 95%. Private cars formed 62.9% of total crashes, shared-taxis formed 26.9%, commercial vehicles formed 8.8%, and the other vehicles such as agricultural, governmental or bikes formed 1.4%. On the other hand, taxis formed only 5.3% of the total vehicle mix in Nablus in year 2016 (PCBS, 2017); however, they were involved in more than one fourth of the pedestrian crashes.

Moreover, crash severity is an important indicator to be considered. The injuries in Nablus City were mostly minor or moderate; they formed 95% of total crashes. The KSI (killed or seriously injured) crashes formed 5% during the study period with 51 injuries. By analyzing this indicator according to population, the KSI per 100,000 capita was 5.60. The KSI for pedestrian crashes in Great Britain's cities was 8.53 in 2016 (Department of Transport Statistics, 2017), which is almost twice the value for Nablus. In Brooklyn City it reached 15.4 (New York City Pedestrian Safety Study & Action Plan, 2015).

Comparing the genders with ages, it has found that for those between the age of 20 and 60 years old, the percentage of pedestrian females involved in crashes was higher than the percentage of males. On the other hand, pedestrian males were more involved in pedestrian crashes for ages less than 20 years and older than 60 years (see Figure 7).

Figure 7. Percentage of Crashes by Gender vs. Age in Nablus City

On the other hand, comparing the genders with severity, it was found that the overall percentage of females involved in crashes with minor injuries was more than males as shown in Figure 8. On the other hand, males generally were more involved in the other categories of moderate, serious, or killed injuries than females.

Figure 8. Percentage of Crashes by Gender vs. Severity in Nablus City

To draw a spatial profile of pedestrian crashes in the city, it was divided into 27 zones depending on the nature of activities, people’s movement, and road network; therefore, the city will be analyzed more accurately. This also was generally consistent with the city’s zoning prepared by Nablus Municipality.

Nablus City had 1030 pedestrian crashes during the period of analysis (2012-2016). However, in analyzing cities’ pedestrian crashes, it is clarified by three questions; Where? When? Who?

Spatially, Figure 9 shows the distribution of these crashes in the 27 zones during the study period. It is clear that Zone 1 (CBD) was the most critical and hazardous zone, which had 18.5% of the total pedestrian crashes in the city, followed by zones 2 (Sufian St. Area) and 5 (New Campus Area) with percentages of 10.4% and 8.6%, respectively. These categories were classified depending on the GIS analysis in dividing data into a relative scale. Critical zones will be analyzed later in a full profile for each.

To test the statistical significance of data for these zones, ANOVA test was used, as shown in Table (1). As shown, F is larger than F critical, which means that one of the groups is statistically different. Moreover, P value is smaller than alpha (0.05), which means that the groups are statistically different at higher than 95% level. Since the zones are statistically different (at 95% significance level); therefore, the zones could be analyzed individually through their profiles.

Figure 9. Pedestrian Crash Distribution by Zones in Nablus City (2012-2016)

Table 1. Results of ANOVA Test

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	7697.659	26	296.0638	31.72112	3.17E-39	1.598423
Within Groups	1008	108	9.333333			
Total	8705.659	134				

Table 2 shows the number of pedestrian crashes along the main (arterial and collector) roads and the critical areas in Nablus City zones for the study period.

Table 2. Pedestrian Crashes in Selected Main Locations in Nablus City (2012-2016)

Road Name	Number of Pedestrian Crashes	% of Total Pedestrian Crashes
Faisal St.	122	11.82%
Rafedia St.	85	8.24%
Al Shuhada' Square	52	5.04%
Omar Bin Khattab St.	43	4.17%
Al Quds St.	40	3.88%
Sufian St.	32	3.10%
Ras Al Ein St.	27	2.62%

The rate of crashes in the city's zones could be analyzed per area, population, or traffic volume. It is concluded that the rate per area would be more applicable in the case of Nablus City due to the nature of people and traffic movement. For the purpose of this analysis, some zones were combined, as quarters, as shown in Figure 10.

By analyzing pedestrian crashes per km², it is found that the CBD area was the most critical one in the city, followed by Rafedia zone and Jaffa Street zone. The CBD had 235.6 pedestrian crashes per km² in the five-year period; this could be explained by the high traffic volume there and the heavy pedestrian activities in the in the limited space area almost all day long.

Figure 10. Analysis of Pedestrian Crashes per km²

In terms of the crash rate per capita, Nablus City had an average of 135 pedestrian crashes per 100,000 capita per year. The spatial distribution shows that the CBD area had 3.52 crashes per 1000 capita per year, Jaffa (2.88), An-Najah National University new campus area (2.16), and Rafedia (1.46), as shown in Figure 11. These areas are well-known in the city of being very active in traffic and pedestrian movements, and a considerable portion of traffic passes through these areas.

Figure 11. Analysis of Pedestrian Crashes per 1000 capita

Approximately, 7% of pedestrian crashes resulted in serious injury or fatality. Although, the majority of pedestrian crashes occurred in built-up areas, their severity was higher at the perimeters of the city and in off-peak traffic periods. These are areas and times where traffic volume is relatively low and driving speed is relatively high. It is also found that afternoon hours were the critical ones, which need more considerations and police enforcement, especially in the zones of 19, 21, and 22 that have 5% KSI of pedestrian crashes.

Regarding vehicle type, shared taxis in these critical zones formed more than one fourth to 40% of pedestrian crashes, although they formed less than 6% of the total vehicles in the city. This has to be taken into consideration and stricter law enforcement should be conducted by the traffic police.

There were 51 KSI crashes during the last 5 years, with an overall average KSI of 5.60 per 100,000 capita. The day with the highest KSI crashes was Saturday with 21.7% from total KSI crashes; the least was Friday with 6.5%. There were two peaks in a day; from 13:00 to 14:00 and from 17:00 to 19:00 forming 34.1% of total KSI crashes. The low movement of vehicles and their high speed would increase the chance for crashes. The most hazardous month was August (8 crashes), and the safest was December without any KSI crashes.

In terms of age distribution of KSI crashes, it was found that age group from 1 to 10 years old was the highest with 39.1% of total crashes. The age category older than 40 years formed 43.5% of total KSI crashes in the city. The low attention of traffic rules and vehicles movements by the youngest and oldest groups lead to be more involved in pedestrian KSI crashes. By analyzing the gender of victims or drivers, it's found that 76% of the victims were males and 24% were females.

Spatially, the zones of 1 (Downtown) and 19 (Al Quds St.) had the most number of KSI crashes (5 crashes), zone 200 (Balata Camp) had 4 KSI crashes, and the zones 14 (Al Masaken), 16, 17 (The eastern zones near the industrial area), and 21 (Faisal St.) had 3 KSI crashes each during the study period (2012-2016).

6. Fatalities in Nablus City

During the five years (2012-2016), Nablus City had 19 people killed in pedestrian crashes, with a fatality rate of 2.09 per 100,000 capita. The day with the highest fatalities was Saturday with 31.6% of the total fatalities; the least was Friday without any.

By analyzing the total crashes by hour, it's clear that there was a peak extending from 17:00 to 19:00 forming 31.6% of total fatalities (6 fatalities). The most hazardous months were April and July (4 fatalities). The age group with the most fatal pedestrian crashes was from 1 to 10 years with 42.1% of total fatal pedestrian crashes in the city. The age category older than 40 years formed 52.6% of total fatalities in the city.

By analyzing the gender of victims, it's found that 79% of the victims were males and 24% were females. On the other hand, the drivers who were involved in fatalities crashes in the city were mostly males with a percent of 95%. Zone 1 (Down Town) had the highest number of fatality crashes (4 crashes) followed by zones 14 (Al Masaken), 16 (Industrial Zone), 19 (Al Quds St.) and 21 (Faisal St.); each had 2 fatalities.

7. Conclusions and Recommendations

As overall results, the most frequent day in pedestrian crashes was Thursday, May was the highest month, and the hour of 13:00 to 14:00 was the highest. The age category that was mostly involved in pedestrian crashes was between 6 and 10 years old. The highest pedestrian crashes were in the zones 1, 2, 5, 3, 21, 22, and 19 (Downtown, Sufian St, New Campus, Rafedia, Faisal St, Ras El Ein, and Al Quds St., respectively). The most hazardous roads were Faisal, Rafedia, Omar Khattab, Quds, Sufian, and Ras El Ein.

The results of pedestrian crashes analysis raise several issues that deserve to be followed up and be further investigated by decision makers and researchers.

- It is highly recommended that traffic police records be fully computerized; the capacity and technology are available at a minimal cost. In addition, it is recommended to use a sound methodology in recording crash data and develop new enhanced data sheet for each crash to include more items, to reduce inaccuracies, to link the pedestrian crashes with the GPS system, and to limit individual's perception, ,
- National level studies should be conducted to investigate the reasons for the increase in the number of pedestrian crashes and fatalities in the West Bank, and identify ways to reduce them.

- The responsible authority (Ministry of Transport, Higher Council for Traffic, etc.) should develop an action plan for the pedestrian safety program at the national level and provide for the appropriate regulatory environment (laws and regulations) in this regard.
- The responsible authorities (Ministry of Transport, Higher Council for Traffic, Traffic Police, Ministry of Education, etc.) should conduct comprehensive traffic safety awareness campaigns targeting drivers and pedestrians, and hold trainings about understanding the factors related to pedestrian crashes, and roles and relationships between pedestrians and drivers. The emphasis should be on priority of the road and compliance to safety measures.
- The relevant authorities should join efforts to implement the traffic law, and stiff penalty should be exerted to reduce these crashes. Appropriate countermeasures, such as traffic calming, engineering solutions, etc., should be implemented to mitigate pedestrian crashes. In addition, existing pedestrian facilities should be maintained and proper facilities (sidewalks, crosswalks, handrails, etc.) should be installed at locations where pedestrians are active and crashes occur frequently.
- It is well known that the available human resources at the traffic police in Nablus are very limited. Therefore, the results of this study could be useful for the traffic police to reallocate the limited available resources and intensify their efforts in the areas and periods that are critical in terms of road safety, particularly for pedestrians; for example, on Thursdays, during the afternoon time, and at the locations of high pedestrian crashes.

8. References

- AASHTO. (2001). A Policy on Geometric Design of Highways and Streets. Washington D.C., USA: American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials.
- Al-Masaeid, H. (2009). Traffic Crashes in Jordan. *Jordan Journal of Civil Engineering*, 3(4): 331-343.
- Al-Omari, H. and Obaidat, E. (2013). Analysis of Pedestrian Crashes in Irbid City, Jordan. *The Open Transportation Journal*, 7: 1-6.
- Andreou, M. (2009). Planning for Pedestrian Safety around Schools, University of New South Wales, Sydney, Australia.
- Davis, R. (2001). National Institutes of Health, North America.
- Fatality Analysis Reporting System (FARS) 2004-2012 Final File, 2013 Annual Report File.
- Garber, N. & Hoel, L. (2009). Traffic and Highway Engineering, 4th edn, Cengage Learning, Virginia, USA.
- Higher Traffic Council (2012). Road Traffic Crashes in the West Bank 2011, Annual Report, Ministry of Transport, Ramallah, Palestine.
- Higher Traffic Council (2013). Road Traffic Crashes in the West Bank 2012, Annual Report, Ministry of Transport, Ramallah, Palestine.
- Higher Traffic Council (2014). Road Traffic Crashes in the West Bank 2013, Annual Report, Ministry of Transport, Ramallah, Palestine.
- Higher Traffic Council (2015). Road Traffic Crashes in the West Bank 2014, Annual Report, Ministry of Transport, Ramallah, Palestine.
- Igazvölgyi, Z. (2015) Increasing Pedestrians' Traffic Safety through Design Parameters. Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Hungary.
- Khader H. (2014). Reality of Road Safety Conditions at Critical Locations in Nablus City with a Roadmap for Future Interventions, Master Thesis, An-Najah National University, Nablus, Palestine.

Knoblauch, R.L., Nitzburg, M., and Seifert, R.F. (2001). Pedestrian Crosswalk Case Studies: Richmond, Virginia; Buffalo, New York; Stillwater, Minnesota, Report No. FHWA-RD-00-103, Federal Highway Administration, Washington, DC, USA.

Kobari, F. (2000). Developing a Safety Management Tool Using a Geographic Information System (GIS), Master Thesis, An-Najah National University, Nablus, Palestine.

New York City Department of Transportation. (2015). The New York City Pedestrian Safety Study & Action Plan Report, New York, USA.

NHTSA; National Highway Traffic Safety Administration. (2014). Traffic Safety Facts, 2014. US Department of Transportation, Washington, DC, USA.

NHTSA; National Highway Traffic Safety Administration. (2015). Traffic Safety Facts, 2015. US Department of Transportation, Washington, DC, USA.

Obeng-Atuah, D. Pedestrian crossing in urban Ghana: Safety Implications, *Journal of Transport and Health*, Vol. 5, 2016, 55-69.

Palestinian Central Bureau of Statistics (PCBS). (2011). Transport & Communications Statistics in the Palestinian Territories Annual Report 2011, Palestinian Central Bureau of Statistics, Ramallah, Palestine, 2012.

Palestinian Central Bureau of Statistics (PCBS). (2016). Transport & Communications Statistics in the Palestinian Territories Annual Report 2015, Palestinian Central Bureau of Statistics, Ramallah, Palestine.

Palestinian Central Bureau of Statistics (PCBS). (2017), Transport & Communications Statistics in the Palestinian Territories Annual Report 2016, Palestinian Central Bureau of Statistics, Ramallah, Palestine.

Palestinian Central Bureau of Statistics (PCBS). (2018). Preliminary Census Results, PHC 2017 Report 2011, Palestinian Central Bureau of Statistics, Ramallah, Palestine.

Tracy, E. (2012). Effects of Pedestrian Perceptions of Safety: An Examination of Pedestrian Crossing Behavior in Marked versus Unmarked Crosswalks, a thesis in Urban Studies and Planning, University of California at San Diego, California, USA.

Zegeer, C., Steward, J., and Lagerwey, P. (2011). Safety Effect of Marked versus Unmarked Crosswalks at Uncontrolled Locations: Analysis of Pedestrian Crashes in 30 Cities. *Journal of the Transportation Research Board*, 1773(1): 56-68.